

CULTURAL DIPLOMACY THROUGH TOURISM: ENHANCING COOPERATION AMONG TURKIC STATES

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Abstract. *This paper discusses the role of tourism as a tool for cultural diplomacy in fostering cooperation among Turkic states. It explores the potential of tourism to boost dynamic of mutual understanding, strengthen cultural ties, and contribute to regional stability. Also, tourism considering as a strategic instrument for the realization of common goals of the Organization of Turkic States. The paper is concluded by providing practical recommendations and suggestions.*

Keywords: *cultural diplomacy, tourism, Turkic states, cooperation.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье обсуждается роль туризма как инструмента культурной дипломатии в укреплении сотрудничества между тюркскими государствами. В ней исследуется потенциал туризма для повышения динамики взаимопонимания, укрепления культурных связей и содействия региональной стабильности. Также туризм рассматривается как стратегический инструмент для реализации общих целей Организации тюркских государств. Статья завершается, практическими рекомендациями и предложениями.*

Ключевые слова: *культурная дипломатия, туризм, тюркские государства, сотрудничество.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada turizmning turkiy davlatlar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirishda madaniy diplomatiya vositasi sifatidagi roli muhokama qilinadi. U o'zaro tushunish dinamikasini oshirish, madaniy aloqalarni mustahkamlash va mintaqaviy barqarorlikka hissa qo'shish uchun turizm salohiyatini o'rganadi. Shuningdek, turizm Turkiy Davlatlar Tashkilotining umumiy maqsadlarini amalga oshirishda strategik vosita sifatida qaralmoqda. Maqola amaliy tavsiyalar va takliflar bilan yakunlanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Madaniy diplomatiya, turizm, turkiy davlatlar, hamkorlik.*

Introduction. The Organization of Turkic States (OTS) has arisen as a regional entity, bringing together countries with a common linguistic, cultural, and historical tie. As these states are facing with the complexities of contemporary geopolitics, tourism presents itself as a strategic tool for cultural diplomacy, capable of enhancing cooperation and fostering a collective identity among Turkic nations. This paper examines the role of tourism in strengthening cultural ties and contributing to regional stability, with a particular focus on how it can be realized to advance the common goals of the OTS member-states.

Historical Context of Turkic Cooperation. After the dissolution of the USSR in the early 1990s Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Türkiye, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan established diplomatic ties with each other and Türkiye. As a result, a summit of heads of state was held in 1992, which contributed to the launch of the process of institutionalization and the creation of the Cooperation Council of Turkic Speaking States in 2009. In 2021 its name was to the Organization of Turkic States (OTS).

The organization, having undergone transformation and gained momentum since its formation, presents considerable potential to its members in various areas. While cultural values

were initially highlighted, today, political and economic expectations play a central role in ensuring the organization’s continuity and effectiveness.

In the Nakhchivan Agreement on the Establishment of Cooperation Council of Turkic Speaking States is declared, that “... the interaction within the common structure facilitates the disclosure of huge potential for good-neighborhood, unity and cooperation among states and their peoples” [5]. In this regards we will analyze the role of tourism as a strategic tool for cultural diplomacy to promote cultural exchange and economic integration on regional level.

The Role of Tourism in Cultural Diplomacy. As it is known, the main driving force in strengthening political and economic ties between member states in the Turkic world is common cultural values. In this context tourism plays a vital role in cultural diplomacy by fostering mutual understanding, building trust, and promoting sustainable regional cooperation among nations. Tourism serves as a means of reconnecting Turkic peoples with their shared history and cultural heritage. This idea is related to the constructivists approach [4]. Identity affects the behaviors of states in international relations and helps them determine their positions [7]. By adopting collective identities, states can act collectively and build institutions in which they can act collectively [3].

Tourism in this context is considered not only as one of the sources of economic income for the Turkic republics, but also as a means of strengthening their social ties (people-to-people interaction). According to social constructivists, the structures that shape the social world are based on common opinions, not on material elements, and the identities and interests of social subjects are not predetermined; instead, they arise in the course of social interaction [4]. By creating conditions for the development of tourism activities in these countries, it is possible to achieve dynamics in the bounding of people, which leads to the strengthening of a common culture, identity and language. Thus, tourism promotes interaction and the protection of common interests among the countries of the Turkic world.

Talking about economic benefits, tourism sector contributes to job creation, infrastructure development, and foreign exchange earnings, which can enhance economic stability and reduce dependence on external powers. For the Turkic states, which are strategically located at the crossroads of Europe and Asia, tourism offers an opportunity to showcase their cultural heritage while fostering regional cooperation.

Current Trends in Turkic Tourism. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in intra-regional tourism among Turkic states. Initiatives such as the “Modern Silk Road” tourism project and the annual Turkic World Tourism Forum have been instrumental in promoting tourism within the region. These efforts are supported by the OTS, which has prioritized tourism as one of the key areas of cooperation in its strategic plan [6].

According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization, tourism arrivals in the Turkic states have seen steady growth, with Kazakhstan and Türkiye being the most popular destinations. In 2023, Kazakhstan recorded over 9 million international tourist arrivals, a significant increase from previous years. Türkiye, with its rich historical sites and vibrant cultural scene, remains a top destination, attracting over 45 million international tourists annually [2].

However, the potential for further growth remains substantial. The Turkic states possess a wealth of untapped tourism resources, including UNESCO World Heritage sites, natural landscapes, and cultural festivals. By developing these assets and improving infrastructure, the Turkic states have a huge potential to enhance their tourism offerings and attract more visitors from within the region and beyond.

Challenges and Opportunities. One of the primary challenges is the lack of adequate infrastructure, particularly in the less developed regions of Central Asia. The most important are the lack of supply chain and logistics facilities, underdeveloped infrastructure and low standard services for tourists [1].

Next is the need for coordinated marketing and promoting tourism industries, there is a lack of a unified approach to marketing the Turkic world as a cohesive tourism destination. The OTS can play a crucial role in addressing this gap by developing joint marketing campaigns, organizing cross-border tourism initiatives, and facilitating collaboration between national tourism boards.

On the other hand, the shared cultural and historical heritage of the Turkic world provides a strong foundation for developing thematic tourism routes, such as the "Silk Road Heritage Tour" or the "Turkic World Cultural Festival Circuit." These initiatives can attract tourists interested in exploring the rich cultural tapestry of the region and provide a platform for showcasing the diverse traditions and customs of the Turkic peoples.

Furthermore, the growing emphasis on sustainable tourism and "green" technologies presents an opportunity for the Turkic states to position themselves as leaders in eco-tourism. By adopting environmentally friendly practices and promoting the conservation of natural and cultural resources, the Turkic states can attract a new segment of tourists who prioritize sustainability in their travel choices.

Recommendations

To maximize the potential of tourism as a tool for cultural diplomacy among Turkic states, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Invest in improving transportation links, accommodation, and tourist facilities, particularly in less developed regions. Public-private partnerships can be a viable option for financing these projects.
2. Develop a unified branding strategy for the Turkic world as a tourism destination. The OTS should coordinate marketing campaigns that highlight the shared cultural heritage and promote cross-border tourism.
3. Organize cultural festivals, exhibitions, and exchange programs that bring together artists, scholars, and cultural practitioners from across the Turkic world.
4. The Turkic states should collaborate on conservation initiatives and sustainable tourism projects that protect the region's natural and cultural resources.
5. Provide training and capacity-building programs for tourism professionals in the Turkic states. This includes language training, customer service skills, and knowledge of sustainable tourism practices.

Conclusion. Tourism holds significant potential as a tool for cultural diplomacy among Turkic states. By fostering mutual understanding, strengthening cultural ties, and contributing to economic development, tourism can play a crucial role in enhancing cooperation within the Turkic world. However, to fully realize this potential, it is important to address the challenges of infrastructure development, coordinated marketing, and sustainable tourism practices. Through strategic investments and collaborative efforts, the Turkic states can leverage tourism to promote cultural diplomacy and achieve their shared goals.

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